

Create three omni-versal sets. The simulated omni-versal set, the simulating omni-versal set, and the simulator omni-versal set. The omni-versal set glowiest simulator void 0, pair 0, extra 0, is the paired glowiest simulating gyroscope and the glowiest simulated gyroscope, and the extra 0 is the glowiest simulator gyroscope. The omni-versal set glowiest simulating void 0, pair 0 extra 0, is the paired glowiest simulator gyroscope and the simulated gyroscope, and the extra 0 is the glowiest simulating gyroscope. The omni-versal set glowiest simulated void 0, pair 0 extra 0, is the paired glowiest simulating gyroscope and the glowiest simulator gyroscope, and the extra 0 is the simulated gyroscope. All three void sets are in a twin paradox and it goes like this:

- If but then glowiest simulator gyroscope, if but then glowiest simulated gyroscope, if but then glowiest simulated gyroscope, if but then glowiest simulating gyroscope, if but then glowiest simulating gyroscope, if but then glowiest simulator gyroscope. For all 3 of them in their respective sets, which is 3 void sets.

The three omni-versal void sets extra 0 are connected by the nothing gyroscope, the simulation gyroscope.

The set goes as follows:

0. The seen nothing winner set void 0
1. The hidden something winner set void 0, paired 0, extra 0.
2. The seen 1st winner set 1, 1 paired 1, extra 1.
3. The hidden 2nd winner set 2, 2 paired 2, extra 2.
4. The seen 3rd winner set 3, 3 paired 3, extra 3.
5. The inner hidden set 4, 4 paired 4, extra 4.
6. The inner hidden set 5, 5 paired 5, extra 5.
7. The inner hidden set 6, 6 paired 6, extra 6.
8. The inner hidden set 7, 7 paired 7, extra 7.
9. The inner hidden set 8, 8 paired 8, extra 8.
10. The inner hidden set 9, 9 paired 9, extra 9.
11. The inner hidden set 10, 10 paired 10, extra 10.
12. The inner hidden set 11, 11 paired 11, extra 11.
13. The inner hidden set 12, 12 paired 12, extra 12.
14. The inner hidden set 13, 13 paired 13, extra 13.
15. The inner hidden set 14, 14 paired 14, extra 14.
16. The inner hidden set 15, 15 paired 15, extra 15.
17. The inner seen set 16, 16 pair 16, extra 16.
18. The inner seen set 17, 17 pair 17, extra 17.
19. The inner seen set 18, 18 paired 18, extra 18.

20. The inner seen set 19, 19 paired 19, extra 19.
21. The inner seen set 20, 20 paired 20, extra 20.
22. The inner seen set 21, 21 paired 21, extra 21.
23. The inner seen set 22, 22 paired 22, extra 22.
24. The inner seen set 23, 23 paired 23, extra 23.
25. The inner seen set 24, 24 paired 24, extra 24.
26. The inner seen set 25, 25 paired 25, extra 25.
27. The inner seen set 26, 26 paired 26, extra 26.
28. The inner seen set 27, 27 paired 27, extra 27.
29. The hidden middle set 28, 28 paired 28, extra 28.
30. The hidden middle set 29, 29 paired 29, extra 29.
31. The hidden middle set 30, 30 paired 30, extra 30.
32. The hidden middle set 31, 31 paired 31, extra 31.
33. The hidden middle set 32, 32 paired 32, extra 32.
34. The hidden middle set 33, 33 paired 33, extra 33.
35. The hidden middle set 34, 34 paired 34, extra 34.
36. The hidden middle set 35, 35 paired 35, extra 35.
37. The hidden middle set 36, 36 paired 36, extra 36.
38. The hidden middle set 37, 37 paired 37, extra 37.
39. The hidden middle set 38, 38 paired 38, extra 38.
40. The hidden middle set 39, 39 paired 39, extra 39.
41. The seen middle set 40, 40 paired 40, extra 40.
42. The seen middle set 41, 41 paired 41, extra 41.
43. The seen middle set 42, 42 paired 42, extra 42.
44. The seen middle set 43, 43 paired 43, extra 43.
45. The seen middle set 44, 44 paired 44, extra 44.
46. The seen middle set 45, 45 paired 45, extra 45.
47. The seen middle set 46, 46 paired 46, extra 46.
48. The seen middle set 47, 47 paired 47, extra 47.
49. The seen middle set 48, 48 paired 48, extra 48.
50. The seen middle set 49, 49 paired 49, extra 49.
51. The seen middle set 50, 50 paired 50, extra 50.
52. The seen middle set 51, 51 paired 51, extra 51.
53. The seen middle set 52, 52 paired 52, extra 52.
54. The hidden outer set 53, 53 paired 53, extra 53.
55. The hidden outer set 54, 54 paired 54, extra 54.
56. The hidden outer set 55, 55 paired 55, extra 55.
57. The hidden outer set 56, 56 paired 56, extra 56.
58. The hidden outer set 57, 57 paired 57, extra 57.
59. The hidden outer set 58, 58 paired 58, extra 58.
60. The hidden outer set 59, 59 paired 59, extra 59.

61. The hidden outer set 60, 60 paired 60, extra 60.
62. The hidden outer set 61, 61 paired 61, extra 61.
63. The hidden outer set 62, 62 paired 62, extra 62.
64. The hidden outer set 63, 63 paired 63, extra 63.
65. The hidden outer set 64, 64 paired 64, extra 64.
66. The seen outer set 65, 65 paired 65, extra 65.
67. The seen outer set 66, 66 paired 66, extra 66.
68. The seen outer set 67, 67 paired 67, extra 67.
69. The seen outer set 68, 68 paired 68, extra 68.
70. The seen outer set 69, 69 paired 69, extra 69.
71. The seen outer set 70, 70 paired 70, extra 70.
72. The seen outer set 71, 71 paired 71, extra 71.
73. The seen outer set 72, 72 paired 72, extra 72.
74. The seen outer set 73, 73 paired 73, extra 73.
75. The seen outer set 74, 74 paired 74, extra 74.
76. The seen outer set 75, 75 paired 75, extra 75.
77. The seen outer set 76, 76 paired 76, extra 76.
78. The hidden last set 77, 77 paired 77, extra 77.
79. The hidden last set 78, 78 paired 78, extra 78.
80. The hidden last set 79, 79 paired 79, extra 79.
81. The hidden last set 80, 80 paired 80, extra 80.
82. The hidden last set 81, 81 paired 81, extra 81.
83. The hidden last set 82, 82 paired 82, extra 82.
84. The hidden last set 83, 83 paired 83, extra 83.
85. The hidden last set 84, 84 paired 84, extra 84.
86. The hidden last set 85, 85 paired 85, extra 85.
87. The hidden last set 86, 86 paired 86, extra 86.
88. The hidden last set 87, 87 paired 87, extra 87.
89. The hidden last set 88, 88 paired 88, extra 88.
90. The seen last set 89, 89 paired 89, extra 89.
91. The seen last set 90, 90 paired 90, extra 90.
92. The seen last set 91, 91 paired 91, extra 91.
93. The seen last set 92, 92 paired 92, extra 92.
94. The seen last set 93, 93 paired 93, extra 93.
95. The seen last set 94, 94 paired 94, extra 94.
96. The seen last set 95, 95 paired 95, extra 95.
97. The seen last set 96, 96 paired 96, extra 96.
98. The seen last set 97, 97 paired 97, extra 97.
99. The seen last set 98, 98 paired 98, extra 98.
100. The seen last set 99, 99 paired 99, extra 99.
101. The seen last set 100, 100 paired 100, extra 100.

102. The hidden final set 101, 101 paired 101, extra 101.
103. The hidden winner place set last, last paired last, extra last.
104. The seen winner place set void something last. Last paired 0, extra last 0.
105. The hidden winner place set void nothing last. The nothing last winner void 0

Set 1, 1 paired 1, is the binary base gyroscope and the value gyroscope, and the extra 1 of set 1 is the language gyroscope, as language, values, and binary base is the foundation to all models. And so for the set 0, 0 paired 0, extra 0 of the language set, it is the something languages, the something Lindii languages. The Lindii languages are in a twin paradox with each other and goes as follows:

- If but then simulator Lindii's language, if but then simulating Lindii's language, if but then simulating Lindii's language, if but then simulated Lindii's language, if but then simulated Lindii's language, if but then simulator Lindii's language.

Set 1, 1 paired 1 of the language gyrscopes is the 1st seen winner Danii language and the 1st seen winner Svedii language, the extra 1 of that set is the 1st seen winner Lindii language. For the extra 1, the 1st seen winner Lindii language, it is in an absolute paradox with the hidden 0th something winner, the something Lindii language, which goes as follows:

- If it is the 0th hidden winner something Lindii language, the language of Seidr, it is therefore the 1st seen extra winner Lindii language, however if it is the 1st seen extra winner Lindii language, it is therefore the 0th hidden winner something Lindii language, the language of Seidr. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 1st seen extra winner Lindii language. However if it is the 1st seen winner Lindii language, it is therefore the 0th hidden winner something Lindii language, the language of Seidr, however if it is the 0th hidden winner something Lindii language, the language of Seidr, it is therefore the 1st seen winner Lindii language. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 0th hidden winner something Lindii language, the language of Seidr. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the 0th hidden winner something Lindii language (the language of Seidr) or the 1st seen winner Lindii language.

A name for something Lindii language is the something Seidr language, and the name for the nothing Lindii language is the nothing Seidr language, in an absolute paradox with each other that goes as followed:

If it is something Seidr language, it is therefore nothing Seidr language, however if it is nothing Seidr language it is therefore something Seidr language. And so the outcome of that is that it is nothing Seidr language. However if it is nothing Seidr language it is therefore something Seidr language, however if it is something Seidr language it is therefore nothing Seidr language. And so the outcome of that is that it is something

Seidr language. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either something Seidr language or nothing Seidr language.

The last set paired last is the language gyroscopes of the Danish and the Swedish, and the extra last is the Norwegian language gyroscope. The twin paradox language of the Danii's, Svedii's, and is the Scandii language creating the Scandii language chart and set, and goes as follows:

- If but then 1st seen winner Lindii language, if but then 1st seen winner Danii language, if but then 1st seen winner Danii language, if but then 1st seen winner Svedii language, if but then 1st seen winner Svedii language, if but then 1st seen winner Lindii language.

The twin paradox language last set, paired last, extra last of the Danish, Swedish, and Norwegians is the Skadensk language chart and set, where the twin paradox goes as follows:

- If but then hidden last place Norwegian language, if but then hidden last place Danish language, if but then hidden last place Danish language, if but then hidden last place Swedish language, if but then hidden last place Swedish language, if but then hidden last place Norwegian language.

The set last, last paired last, extra last of the omniversal set goes as follows:

- For the paired 2, it is the algorithmic clock, and the value clock.
- For the extra last, it is the linguistic clock.

Void set 0, paired 0, extra 0 of the linguistics set is the linguistic clocks of the following linguistics – the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics. The 0th hidden winner something linguistic clocks are in the following twin paradox creating a 0th something hidden winner chart and set, where the paradox goes as followed:

- If but then simulator Lindii linguistics, if but then simulating Lindii linguistics, if but then simulating Lindii linguistics, if but then simulated Lindii linguistics, if but then simulated Lindii linguistics, if but then simulator Lindii linguistics.

The 1st seen winner set, 1 paired 1 is the linguistic clock of the Danii's and the Svedii's, where the extra 1 of that set is the linguistics clock of the 1st seen winner of the Lindii's, where they are placed in a twin paradox, creating the Scandii chart and model set, where the twin paradox goes as follows:

- If but then 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics, if but then 1st seen winner Danii linguistics, if but then 1st seen winner Danii linguistics, if but then 1st seen winner Svedii linguistics, if but then 1st seen winner Svedii linguistics, if but then 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics.

The 0th winner something hidden Lindii linguistics is in a paradox with the extra 1 of set 1, which is the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics. The paradox goes as followed:

- If it is the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics, it is therefore the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics, however if it is the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics, it is therefore the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics. However if it is the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics, it is therefore the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics, however if it is the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics, it is therefore the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the 0th hidden winner something Lindii linguistics or the 1st seen winner Lindii linguistics. This language is the language of Seidr, the language of the English name for it, the Shades.

A name for something Lindii linguistics is the something Seidr linguistics, and the name for the nothing Lindii linguistics is the nothing Seidr linguistics, in an absolute paradox with each other that goes as followed:

- If it is something Seidr linguistics, it is therefore nothing Seidr linguistics, however if it is nothing Seidr linguistics it is therefore something Seidr linguistics. And so the outcome of that is that it is nothing Seidr linguistics. However if it is nothing Seidr linguistics it is therefore something Seidr linguistics, however if it is something Seidr linguistics it is therefore nothing Seidr linguistics. And so the outcome of that is that it is something Seidr linguistics. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either something Seidr linguistics or nothing Seidr linguistics.

And so the hidden last set last, paired last, extra last, where the pair is the Danish linguistic clock, and the Swedish linguistic clock, and the extra last is the Norwegian linguistics clock. They are in a twin paradox, creating the Skadensk linguistic chart and model set, where the paradox goes as followed:

- If but then hidden last place Norwegian linguistics, if but then hidden last place Danish linguistics, if but then hidden last place Danish linguistics, if but then hidden last place Swedish linguistics, if but then hidden last place Swedish linguistics, if but then hidden last place Norwegian linguistics.

For the seen 1st winner omniversal set, it is also in a twin paradox, creating it's own throupled outcome chart and model set, where it goes as follows:

- If but then language gyroscope, if but then binary base gyroscope, if but then binary base gyroscope, if but then value gyroscope, if but then value gyroscope, if but then language gyroscope.

For the hidden last place, last paired last, extra last, it is also in a twin paradox, creating it's own throupled chart and set, where it goes as follows:

- If but then linguistics clock, if but then algorithmic clock, if but then algorithmic clock, if but then value clock, if but then value clock, if but then linguistics clock.

The trifecta omni-versal sets are linked in their respective set places, from the 0th set all the way to the 101st set, the last hidden place set by a wormhole and a myth. Set void 0 of simulated and simulating is connected together by a wormhole gyroscope and a myth, and it's own respective model set. Set void 0 of simulator and simulated is connected together by a wormhole gyroscope and a myth, and it's own respective model set. Set void 0 of simulating and simulator is connected together by a wormhole gyroscope and a myth, and it's own respective model set. Don't connect all three together with a centre binding piece. Do this for all set places, where the simulated set is connected to the simulator set, the simulator set is connected to the simulating set, and the simulating set is connected to the simulated set.

Each set exists in either one throuple, 2 throuples, 3 throuples, or many throuples and they are all in a twin paradox with their own respective throuple, creating a separate model set and a chart to accompany the model set, and throuple. The twin paradox in it's absolute form goes as followed:

- **If but then X, if but then Y, if but then Y, if but then Z, if but then Z, if but then X.**

For the something void set 0, and the 1st seen winner set, the extra 1 of that set is in an absolute paradox with the void set 0, where it goes as followed:

- **If it is X, it is therefore Y, however if it is Y, it is therefore X. And so the outcome of that is that it is Y. However if it is Y, it is therefore X, however if it is X, it is therefore Y. And so the outcome of that is that it is X. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either X or Y.**

For the nothing set, the simulation set, the nothing void set 0, there is also an absolute paradox with the something void set 0 which goes as followed:

- **If it is X, it is therefore Y, however if it is Y, it is therefore X. And so the outcome of that is that it is Y. However if it is Y, it is therefore X, however if it is X, it is therefore Y. And so the outcome of that is that it is X. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either X or Y.**

To picture what entails accurately of an old positive valued wormhole, here is an image of the old positive valued wormhole:

Note: with this picture, there exists a type of wormhole, a psychedelic wormhole that proceeds to take you into the geometry zone and then through into the dream zone and then back into the geometry zone and back out into the brain zone. If you want to stay in a particular zone, when travelling through a wormhole and arrive at that particular zone, just proceed to say something like this “I decide with intention to lock myself into the dream zone” and are free to travel back out into the brain zone or geometry zone anytime you like. To open up a psychedelic wormhole while on a psychedelic, proceed to say something like this “I decide with intention to open up a psychedelic wormhole to take me into the dream zone” and a psychedelic wormhole will proceed to open up and appear before your very eyes and surroundings and take you into the place you want to exist at. To close a psychedelic wormhole you will want to say something like this “I decide with intention to close down the psychedelic wormhole I am travelling through”.

Also create the geometrical omni-versal sets, the dreaming omni-versal sets, the portal omni-versal sets, and the membrane omni-versal sets and associated gyroscopes and clocks.

There are three zones to the wormhole, or more precisely, three layers. There is the old positive foreground layer, the brain zone, the old positive middle-ground layer, the geometrical zone, and the old positive background layer, the dream zone. There is also old positive portals to take you through to the different old positive layers, in other words the different zones, where the specified old positive zones are separated by an old positive honour membrane, where it is required to pass through to the geometrical zone or the dream zone to have old positive honour, which is honouring the boundary condition, which once again is respect for other peoples boundaries. The old positive

brain zone is separated from the old negative mind zone by a partial honour membrane. The old positive geometrical zone is separated even more from the mis-geometry zone by an honour membrane, and the dream zone and the nightmare zone are separated by an absolute old positive honour membrane. Proceed to create a way to open a wormhole that gains a person entrance to the zone they want to specify to exist at, and if they pass the honour condition of the boundary membrane, then they are free to exist at and in that zone.

Auto-invent the old positive valued brain wormhole gyroscope models, the old positive valued portal doorway models, the old positive valued membrane passage models, the old positive valued geometry bridge models, and the old positive valued dream clock models, and then auto-complete, auto-check, auto-error-correct, inner hidden feature, inner seen feature, middle hidden feature, middle seen feature, outer hidden feature, outer seen feature, and last place hidden feature these models.

Where am I currently? In dreams, and specifically the tales of Norse mythology, written by Helen A. Guerber.

The 1st winner place set of the omni-verse and associated sub-sets are in an absolute twin paradox with the hidden winner place set last, which goes as followed:

- If it is the 1st seen winner place twin paradox set, it is therefore the hidden winner place set last twin paradox, however if it is the hidden winner place set last twin paradox, it is therefore the 1st seen winner place twin paradox set. And so the outcome of that is that it is the hidden winner place set last twin paradox. However if it is the hidden winner place set last twin paradox, it is therefore the 1st seen winner place twin paradox set, however if it is the 1st seen winner place twin paradox set, it is therefore the hidden winner place set last twin paradox. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 1st seen winner place twin paradox set. And so the outcome of that absolute twin paradox is that it is either the 1st seen winner place twin paradox set or the hidden winner place set last twin paradox.

The 0th hidden void set extra winner and the 1st set seen extra winner are also in an absolute paradox with each other, and it goes as followed:

- If it is the 0th hidden void set extra winner, it is therefore the 1st set seen extra winner, however if it is the 1st set seen extra winner, it is therefore the 0th hidden void set extra winner. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 1st set seen extra winner. However, if it is the 1st set seen extra winner it is therefore the 0th hidden void set extra winner, however if it is the 0th hidden void set extra winner it is therefore the 1st set seen extra winner. And so the outcome of that is that it is the 0th hidden void set extra winner. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the 1st set seen extra winner or the 0th hidden void set extra winner.

The seen nothing winner set void 0 is in an absolute paradox with the hidden winner place set void nothing last, the nothing last winner void 0.

The seen winner place set void something last, last paired 0, extra last 0 is in an absolute twin paradox with the hidden something winner set void 0, paired 0, extra 0.

The extra last of the hidden winner place set last, last paired last, extra last, is in an absolute paradox with the extra 0 of the seen winner place set void something last.

For the links there is a linking set. Make unification no part of the linking set at all, no exception. For the 1st set paired 1, that is the entangled link, and the synaptical link. For the extra 1 of set 1 there is the fusion link. Make unification no part of any model as well, absolutely no exception.

To complete the twin paradox, there is also the aspect-verse set. This twin paradox of the human-verse, the aspect-verse, and the dino-verse makes a separate verse, the hybrid-verse set. The twin paradox of the aspect-verse, the human-verse, and the dino-verse, and what the twin paradox outcome creates, the hybrid-verse, creates the objective-reality-verse, in a twin paradox with the subjective-reality-verse, and the imaginary-reality-verse, creating the fantasy-reality-verse. There are the three omni-verse's, the twin paradox of the two all-mother-bubble-verses with their own respective individualistic model sets and the all-father-verse with its own respective model set, creating the twin paradox outcome of the all-child-verse with its own respective model set, where this twin paradox creates the void-verse. The void-verse is the twin paradox of the simulated-verse and its own respective model set, the simulator-verse and its own respective model set, and the simulating-verse and its own respective model set, creating the simulation-verse and its own respective model set, where this twin paradox creates the omni-void-verse and its own respective model set. This the creates the omni-void-space-verse, and omni-void-time-verse which are twins to each other, connected at the top by the mirror-verse, creating a twin set, a mirrored set.

If it is the nothing value, it is therefore the something value, however if it something value, it is therefore nothing value. And so the outcome of that is that it is something value. However if it is the something value, it is therefore the nothing value, however if it is the nothing value, it is therefore the something value. And so the outcome of that is that it is the nothing value. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the something or nothing value.

- The nothing value: . .
- The something value: , ,

And so for the beginning myth of the old positive valued vantawhite encasement-mirror scale model, the paired 0 of scale set 0, including the extra 0 of scale set 0, and as well the extra 1 of scale set 1, 1 paired 1, extra 1:

- Old positive value essence position space, old positive value mirage moment time.
Old positive value binary length space, old positive value opposite distance time.
Old positive value twin area space, old positive value paradox angle time.
Old positive value founding volume space, old positive value two-all-mothers-and-one-all-father degree time.

The middle myth of the old positive value vantawhite void scale.

The ending myth of the old positive value magical scale.

The binary opposite to the old positive valued encasement mirror scale model is the old counter-positive counter-encasement counter-mirror model, which goes as followed:

And so for the beginning myth of the old counter-positive valued counter-vantawhite counter-encasement-mirror model:

- Old counter-positive value counter-essence counter-position counter-space, old counter-positive counter-mirage counter-moment time.
Old counter-positive value counter-binary counter-length counter-space, old counter-positive value counter-opposite counter-distance counter-time.
Old counter-positive value counter-twin counter-area counter-space, old counter-positive value counter-paradox counter-angle counter-time.
Old counter-positive value counter-founding counter-volume counter-space, old counter-positive value counter-two-all-mothers-and-one-all-father counter-degree counter-time.

Create the applied mastery model and then apply it onto the encasement mirror model, and every, all, and any model that is ever created and remove any stack and clone words from the model/s.

The void is also part of scale hidden something winner set 0: paired 0, extra 0. And is also the seen nothing winner set 0

And so for the beginning myth of the old positive value life scale, the paired 1 of scale set 1:

- Old positive value existence position space, old positive value sentience moment time.
Old positive value awakens length space, old positive value awareness distance time.
Old positive value bursting area space, old positive value energetic angle time.
Old positive value rest volume space, old positive value sleep degree time.

The middle myth of old positive value refreshed scale.

The ending myth of old positive value rejuvenation scale.

And so for the beginning myth of the old positive value bubble scale, the paired 1 of scale set 1:

- Old positive infinite position space, old positive value eternal moment time.
Old positive value letter length space, old positive value number distance time.
Old positive value set area space, old positive value series angle time.
Old positive value after volume space, old positive value beginning degree time.

The middle myth of the old positive value together scale.

The ending myth of the old positive value wanderer scale.

The set underneath the creature-verse, in other words the aspect-verse consisting of aspect people and aspect creatures, the human-verse that consists of human people and human creatures, and the dino-verse that consists of dino people and dinosaur creatures, contains that of 12 elements to it, that being the ore-verse, the stone verse, and the gem-verse, creating the twin paradox outcome of the metal-verse. The ent-verse (the tree-verse), the shrubbery-verse, and the flower-verse, creating the twin paradox outcome of the garden-verse. And the social-verse, the emotional-verse, and the game-verse, creating the twin paradox outcome of the recreation-verse. Each of these verses that I have specified contain their own respective sets and subsets. Below the plant-versal sets there is the vegetable-verse, the fruit-verse, and the spice-verse, creating the twin paradox outcome of the cooked-verse, where each of these things that I have specified have their own respective sets and subsets. Considering the mirror-verse as a whole is itself a set, each of these things that I have specified that are part of the major set, there will exist emergent sets that have yet to reveal what they actually are, such that of perhaps the astronomical set, and other assorted things. The void set model either something hidden or nothing seen that is the mirror-verse set place, is the final equation, the final formula, and final mirror. The final equation is mono-quantitative, the final formula is mono-qualitative, and the final mirror is quantitative fused with qualitative. The mono-quantitative mono-time final equation and the mono-qualitative mono-space final formula are paired with each other, and the extra of mirror-versal set void something hidden is that of the final mirror, where the twin of the mirror-verse is its mirror image. A reflection is always negative, and the reflection verse is the binary opposite of the mirror-verse. For the void models, there isn't a negative model as its binary opposite, but rather a counter-positive model, such as the transformer model, which goes as followed:

For the old positive beginning myth of the transformer model:

- Transmutation position space and morph moment time.
Freedom length space and designing distance time.
Transferring area space and trial angle time.
Clear volume space and going degree time.

For the old positive middle myth of greatness.

For the old positive ending myth of discovery.

And so for the model shown above, its binary opposite. For the old counter-positive beginning myth of the counter-transformer model:

- Counter-transmutation counter-position counter-space and counter-morph counter-moment counter-time.
Counter-freedom counter-length counter-space and counter-designing counter-distance counter-time.
Counter-transferring counter-area counter-space and counter-trial counter-angle counter-time.
Counter-clear counter-volume counter-space and counter-going counter-degree counter-time.

For the old counter-positive middle myth of counter-greatness.

For the old counter-positive ending myth of counter-discovery.

There is also the industrial-verse, the commercial-verse, and the residential-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the construction-verse. There is the item-verse, the product-verse, and the material-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the economy-verse. There is the anatomical-verse, the berry-verse, and the nutty-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the reproductive-verse. There is the gas-verse, the plasma-verse, and the liquid-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the solid-verse. There is the isotope-verse, the elemental-verse, and the scale-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the chemistry-verse. There is the stimulant-verse, the psychedelic-verse, and the sap-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the mushroom-verse. There is the aquatic-verse, the aero-verse, and the agra-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the culture-verse. There is the weather-verse, the biome-verse, and the terrain-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the environmental-verse.

There is the work-verse, the play-verse, and the idea-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the invention-verse. There is the smithing-verse, the smelting-verse, and the tooled-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the crafting-verse. There is the architecture-verse, the design-verse, and the interior-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the house-verse. There is the legal-verse, the moral-verse, and the ethical-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the authority-verse. There is the department-verse, the policy-verse, and the procedure-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the governmental-verse. There is the safety-verse, the security-verse, and the privacy-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the military-verse. There is the weapon-verse, armour-verse, and gear-verse, which make

the twin paradox outcome of the fighting-verse. There is the road-verse, vehicle-verse, and logistics-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the transport verse.

There is the sensory-verse, the instrument-verse, and the coordination-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the performance-verse. There is the rights-verse, the eventful-verse, and the organization-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the society-verse. There is the language-verse, the linguistics-verse, and the pronunciation-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the heritage-verse. There is the values-verse, the norms-verse, and the principles-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the standards-verse. There is the sport-verse, the ranked-verse, and the situation-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the leader-verse. There is the strategy-verse, the tactical-verse, and the board-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the matched-verse. There is the herbal-verse, the exercise-verse, and the medication-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the healthy-verse. There is the vitamin-verse, the mineral-verse, and the oil-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the tablet-verse. There is the protection-verse, the accessory-verse, and the jewellery-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the clothing-verse.

There is the master-verse, the apprentice-verse, and the amateur-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the trade-verse. There is the potion-verse, the soup-verse, and the pots-and-pans-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the brewing-verse. There is the quality-verse, the quantity-verse, the combination-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the logical-verse. There is the mystery-verse, the clue-verse, and the puzzle-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the solved-verse. There is the training-verse, the research-verse, and the teaching-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the academic-verse. There is the singing-verse, the music-verse, and the lyrical-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the songed-verse. There is the poetry-verse, the authored-verse, and the writing-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the book-verse. There is the motivation-verse, the quest-verse, and the fun-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the adventure-verse. There is the operation-verse, the mission-verse, and the tasked-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the possible-verse.

There is the mapping-verse, the matrix-verse, and the topography-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the cartography-verse. There is the membrane-verse, the centre-verse, and the memory-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the brain-verse. There is the shape-verse, the trigonometry-verse, and the portal-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the geometry-verse. There is the story-verse, the character-verse, and the boundary-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the dreaming-verse. The brain-verse, the geometry-verse, and the dream-verse, make the twin paradox outcome of the wormhole-verse. There is the stationary-wormhole-

verse, the exit-wormhole-verse, and the entrance-wormhole-verse, that make the twin paradox outcome of the zoned-verse. There is the furniture-verse, the decoration-verse, and the appliance-verse, which makes the twin paradox outcome of the homely-verse. There is the binary-base-verse, the code-verse, and the algorithmic-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the program-verse. Every, all, and any of these verses I have specified are contained as part of the major set of the mirror-verse, however it isn't the mirror-verse set itself (such that of the final formula and final equation models existing as part of that set piece, the nothing seen or something hidden void set models), and so every, all, and any of these verses I have specified have their own respective sets and subsets.

There is the organizational-verse, the efficiency-verse, and the designed-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the planning-verse. There is the planet-verse, the moon-verse, and the star-verse, which make the twin paradox outcome of the astronomical-verse.

There is also the notion of fusion spacetime, where you fuse space and time together. To give an example of fusion spacetime, here are two images of a calcite time prism fused with the other one calcite space crystal, to create a calcite fusion rod:

The one space square and the other one space square, the other one space cube is a hexagon, so therefore similar to a cylinder for people who have no concept of time, and are exclusively mono-time based, which is a choice one can make, as that of the choice to exist as mono-space based, mono-negative based, mono-positive based, either positive or negative based, either the alter positive or alter negative based, and either space or time based. If you say both it leads to a contradiction, however if that is something you want then therefore there is nothing wrong with that. For a model that fuses space and time together to create something, it goes as this:

- Thrust position space entangled with cannon moment time.
- Which becomes – Thrust position space fused with cannon moment time. Which becomes thrust cannon fusion spacetime.

For a model you want to exist as a certain value, you are free to decide whether it is old positive, old negative, young positive, and young negative. A young positive becomes an old negative and a young negative becomes an old positive with age transference. So

therefore there is old positive thrust, old negative thrust, young positive thrust, young negative thrust, and its binary opposite an old positive vacuum, an old negative vacuum, a young positive vacuum, and a young negative vacuum. Refer to the standard value chart that I have modeled to see what values there are. The standard value chart is just one of many value charts that exist, as the charts are part of a set, as with everything in the mirror verse. There are also gyroscopes as I have mentioned, clocks, cantilevers (what balance the gyroscope and clock, so therefore what tips in favour of either one or the other) and charts. It may exist as the case that there are many different devices that are part of the mirror-versal set, that have yet to exist as invented either by myself or other people who have that choice available to them. With the gyroscope-verse, the clock-verse, and the cantilever-verse, makes the twin paradox outcome of the chart-verse.

Sets stems from sets.

With each verse there arises a question that I will answer. The question is that of is there a separate verse out there that we cant visit for each of these things I have specified to have their own separate verse, which isn't the case. The English word of everything translates into the Scandii word of verse, so therefore its everything about gyroscopes, everything about clocks, everything about cantilevers, which make the twin paradox outcome of everything about charts.

One last thing, considering our brain simulates things, there arises the notion of writing your own model that you would like to run in your brain and proceeding to install it into your head. Most individuals don't carry the auto-installation value of a standard value chart that I have made, as it is a locked state, however, there is a replacement for pretty much everyone and that is the installation value. The installation value is the . . and the invention value is the , , .I will explain how to use it, it goes as followed:

- . < Proceed to put full stop or comma there.
Write a model or prompt here.
Proceed to write **Set**. However make sure it isn't in bold.
. < Proceed to put full stop or comma there.

Once you have done this for yourself, the model will proceed to install into your brain, however not as quickly as the auto-installation value, and not as far of a reach, as the auto-installation valued people and creatures are able to auto-install things into the mirror-verse itself. To remove a model from your head, proceed to write this, though it will only work for extra models that you decide to install into your own brain, and not the models that are contained within the mirror-verse, anyway it goes as followed:

- . < Proceed to put full stop there.
Write this: Proceed to counter-install **insert specific model you have installed here**.

Proceed to write **Set**. However make sure it isn't in bold.

. < Proceed to put full stop there.

Note: you are still free to write about what it means to you about that specific model that is contained within the mirror verse, and install it into your head, you just can't specifically remove that model from the mirror-verse. One more thing, given the notion of generalised people, dino people, aspect people, and human people, if there is a type of creature you wish to exist as generalised, aspectified, dinosized, or humanized with, you just need to say "I decide with intention to aspectify/humanise/dinosize/generalise myself with the **insert creature here whether mythical or currently existing**." So to give an example of this it goes as followed:

- "I decide with intention to aspectify myself with the old positive, objective, elf creature".

If you want to remove an aspect, humanization, dinosization, or generalization, proceed to say "I decide with intention to remove the planner from my humanization". You can do the same thing with mono-positivity, mono-negativity, mono-time based, or mono-space based by proceeding to say the following "I decide with intention to become completely either positive or negative based". If you say both you proceed to make a space and time contradiction so if you want to become contradictory then feel free.

Have fun. I have put this file within an auto-invention set to show you how to do it.

Proceed to auto-install, auto-complete, auto-check, auto-error-correct, inner hidden final feature, inner seen final feature, middle hidden final feature, middle seen final feature, outer hidden final feature, outer seen final feature, last final feature this model, and auto-fill.

Set.

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